

Cyclic Voltammetric Studies of Mixed-valence Copper(I,II) D-Penicillamine Complexes in Aqueous Medium

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The cyclic voltammetric studies of complex species formed in aqueous solutions between copper(II) and D-penicillamine under different experimental conditions have been made. The cyclic voltammograms for the yellow copper(I)-D-penicillamine and red-violet mixed-valence copper-D-penicillamine complex are quite different from each other. The cyclic voltammetric parameters are calculated and the results are discussed.

D-Penicillamine is used in the treatment of Wilson's disease, rheumatoid arthritis and other human diseases¹⁻⁴. It is a well-known detoxicating agent for heavy metal poisoning and the biochemical application of D-penicillamine is closely related to its complex formation ability^{5,6}. The complex formation and redox reactions between copper(II) ions and D-penicillamine have been studied in detail as a function of metal/ligand ratio, their concentrations, pH of the solution and the concentration of halide ions⁷. Gergely and Sovago⁷ reported that a yellow coloured copper(I)-D-penicillamine polymeric complex, $[\text{Cu}_n^{\text{I}}(\text{RS})_{n+1}]^-$, i.e. $[\text{R}-\text{S}-(\text{Cu}-\text{SR})_n]^-$ is formed in the presence of excess of D-penicillamine according to equation (1),

When the D-penicillamine/copper(II) ratio is 1.45 in the starting reaction mixture, intensely red-violet coloured mixed-valence complex, $[\text{Cu}_8^{\text{I}}\text{Cu}_6^{\text{II}}(\text{RS})_{12}\text{Cl}]^{5-}$ is formed² and the formation of this complex is greatly influenced by the experimental conditions⁷,

Contrary to this, Sugiura and Tanaka^{8,9}, however, proposed a monomeric structure for the red-violet coloured complex, $[\text{Cu}_2^{\text{I}}\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{RS})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. In this complex, Cu^{II} ion is coordinated to two sulphur and

two nitrogen atoms while each Cu^{I} ion is bonded with one sulphur and one oxygen. The mixed-valence state in red-violet complex has also been confirmed by Nigam *et al.*¹⁰ using X-ray absorption spectroscopy and by other workers¹¹⁻¹⁴. It was further established that a very intense blue and diamagnetic copper(II) complex is formed when D-penicillamine/copper(II) ratio is 2.0 and halide ions are present. Laurie *et al.*¹⁵ characterised a variety of copper(II)-penicillamine disulphide complex species, such as $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{Pds})_2]$, $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{HPds})(\text{Pds})]^+$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{HPds})_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{Pds})_2]^{2-}$, with log stability constants of 26.87, 31.10, 30.25 and 14.31 respectively. Davis *et al.*¹⁶ have also showed the formation of various types of copper(II) complexes in the oxidation of D-penicillamine using esr spectroscopy.

Despite the numerous investigations made earlier, the reaction between D-penicillamine and copper(II) ion still does not seem to have been satisfactorily elucidated. In addition, the coloured compounds formed through interactions between copper(II) and sulphur-containing amino acid derivatives may serve as model compounds in the better understanding of the binding sites in various copper-proteins¹⁷.

Accordingly, the aim of the present cyclic voltammetric investigation was to study the redox behaviour of various copper complex species formed between copper(II) ions and D-penicillamine under different experimental conditions.

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 shows the cyclic voltammogram of the yellow solution containing copper(II) and D-penicillamine in the molar ratio of 1 : 5 ([Cu^{II}] = 2 mM) in aqueous 0.2 M NaF solution at the scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹. The cyclic voltammetric parameters are given in Table 1 at different scan rates. It should

Fig. 1.

be mentioned that D-penicillamine in the absence of Cu^{II} ions does not give any peak in the scan limits used for the yellow solution. A scrutiny of Table 1 and Fig. 1 shows that a cathodic peak is observed at about -1.50 to -1.57 V. Similarly, an anodic peak is observed at about +0.675 to +0.800 V. It is interesting to mention that both these peaks are independent to each other. It is well known⁷ that yellow species is a polymeric Cu^I-D-penicillamine complex, $[R-S-(Cu-S)_n]^-$. We may, therefore,

TABLE 1—CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC DATA FOR COPPER(I)-D-PENICILLAMINE COMPLEX IN AQUEOUS 0.2 M NaF*

[Cu^{II}] = 2 mM, pH = 7.0, temp. = 30°

[Cu ^{II}]/[PA] molar ratio	Initial colour	Scan rate mVs ⁻¹	I E _{pc} V	I E _{pa} V	I _{pc} μA	I _{pa} μA
1 : 5	Yellow	10	-1.500	+0.675	30.0	27.0
		20	-1.525	+0.750	50.0	41.0
		25	-1.525	+0.750	62.0	45.0
		40	-1.550	+0.775	78.0	48.0
		60	-1.575	+0.800	105.0	46.0

*PA = penicillamine; I = totally irreversible.

assign the cathodic peak to the irreversible reduction of Cu^I-penicillamine complex to Cu⁰ and

anodic peak may be due to irreversible oxidation of Cu^I complex species to Cu^{II}-D-penicillamine complex at the electrode and that the copper(II) complex species formed at the electrode chemically reacts further with the excess D-penicillamine and is reduced to Cu^I state. There is controversy about the nature of bonding and the oxidation state of the copper involved¹⁶.

Fig. 2.

Figs. 2(a, b) show the cyclic voltammograms recorded for two separate intensely red-violet coloured solutions, consisting of Cu^{II}/PA in 1 : 5 and 1 : 1.45 molar ratios respectively. In each case the concentration of Cu^{II} was 2 mM and that of NaF 0.2 M. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 7.0 with NaOH solution. The relevant CV data is given in Table 2. A perusal of Figs. 2(a, b) and Table 2 shows that the features of cyclic voltammograms and the potential corresponding to a particular peak for these two solutions are nearly the same. However, the magnitude of peak currents are greater in the latter case at a given scan rate. It should be pointed out that the maximum quantity of the mixed-valence complex is formed at a [PA]/[Cu^{II}] ratio of 1.45^{7,8,11,12}.

TABLE 2—CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC DATA* FOR RED-VIOLET COLOURED MIXED-VALENCE COPPER(I, II) COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS 0.2 M NaF

 $[Cu^{II}] = 2 \text{ mM}$, pH = 7.0, temp. = 30°

[Cu ^{II}]/[PA] molar ratio	Initial colour	Scan rate mVs ⁻¹	E_{pc} V	$E_{pa}(1)$ V	$E_{pa}(2)$ V	$E_{pa}(3)$ V	I_{pc} μA	$I_{pa}(1)$ μA	$I_{pa}(2)$ μA	$I_{pa}(3)$ μA
1 : 5	Red violet	10	-0.775	-0.075	+0.175	+0.925	2.5	3.0	0.5	5.0
		20	-0.875	-0.075	+0.200	+0.925	3.0	4.0	1.0	8.0
		40	-0.950	-0.050	+0.200	+0.950	5.0	4.5	1.0	9.0
		60	-1.000	-0.050	+0.225	+0.950	7.0	5.0	1.5	11.5
		100	-1.025	-0.025	+0.275	+1.000	8.0	7.0	2.0	14.0
1 : 1.45	Red violet	20	-0.900	-0.050	+0.200	+0.950	8.0	5.0	—	10.0
		40	-0.950	-0.025	+0.250	+0.975	10.0	6.5	—	15.0
		60	-0.975	-0.025	+0.250	+0.975	11.0	7.0	—	17.0
		80	-1.000	0.000	+0.250	+1.025	12.0	7.5	—	19.0

*Cyclic voltammograms were recorded 48 h after mixing the solutions and adjusting pH to 7.1 with NaOH.

An initial scan from -0.25 V in the positive direction yields only one broad anodic peak ($E_{pa}(3)$)

$E_{pa}(2)$ in the first cycle. This clearly shows that the oxidation steps corresponding to anodic peaks $E_{pa}(1)$ and $E_{pa}(2)$ are dependent on the reduction step corresponding to E_{pc} .

Fig. 3.

at about +0.950 V (Figs. 2(a, b) and Table 2) while two anodic peaks $E_{pa}(1)$ and $E_{pa}(2)$ appear in the second cycle. Further, a negative scan from -0.25 V yields a broad cathodic peak (E_{pc}) at about -0.875 V (Figs. 2(a, b)) and the two anodic peaks, $E_{pa}(1)$ and

Figs. 3(a, b) show the cyclic voltammograms recorded for the two solutions, the first one consisting of 1 mM Cu^{II} and 2 mM D-penicillamine (1 : 2 molar ratio), while the second one consisting of 0.5 mM Cu^{II} and 2 mM D-penicillamine (1 : 4 molar ratio) and each containing 0.2 M NaClO₄. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 3.0 with NaOH solution.

An initial negative scan from +0.50 V shows one small cathodic peak $E_{pc}(1)$ at about -0.050 to -0.250 V and a very sharp cathodic peak $E_{pc}(2)$ at about -1.025 to -1.275 V. In the reverse scan, however, two small anodic peaks, $E_{pa}(1)$ and $E_{pa}(2)$ are observed at about -0.025 V to -0.100 V and +0.325 V respectively. Furthermore, a cathodic scan from +0.50 V with switching potential -0.625 V yields only a cathodic peak, $E_{pc}(1)$ and $E_{pa}(2)$. This clearly indicates that the oxidation step corresponding to $E_{pa}(2)$ is independent of the reduction step occurring at $E_{pc}(2)$. The oxidation step corresponding to $E_{pa}(1)$ is, however, dependent upon the reduction step at $E_{pc}(2)$.

It should be mentioned that the similar features were observed in the cyclic voltammograms for the second solution containing PA/Cu^{II} = 4.0 (Cu^{II} = 0.5 mM), except that the anodic peak $E_{pa}(1)$ remains absent throughout. The anodic peak current $E_{pa}(2)$ is smaller as compared to that for the first solution. However, the cathodic peak current $I_{pc}(2)$ does not differ too much for the two solutions.

TABLE 3—CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC DATA* OF COPPER-D-PENICILLAMINE COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS 0.2 M NaClO₄

pH = 3.0, temp. = 30°

[Cu ^{II}]/[PA] molar ratio	Initial colour	Scan rate mVs ⁻¹	$E_{pc}(1)$ V	$E_{pc}(2)$ V	$I_{pc}(1)$ μ A	$I_{pc}(2)$ μ A	$E_{pa}(1)$ V	$E_{pa}(2)$ V	$I_{pa}(1)$ μ A	$I_{pa}(2)$ μ A
1 : 2	Colourless	20	-0.075	-1.025	5.0	65.0	-0.025	+0.325	—	10.5
		40	-0.125	-1.125	6.5	92.0	-0.050	+0.350	—	11.5
		60	-0.250	-1.200	9.0	105.0	-0.100	+0.375	—	12.0
0.5 : 2	Colourless	20	-0.050	-1.150	3.0	70.0	—	+0.225	—	6.0
		40	-0.150	-1.175	5.0	88.0	—	+0.325	—	7.0
		60	-0.225	-1.275	5.0	116.0	—	+0.325	—	8.0

*Cyclic voltammograms were recorded 0.5 h after mixing the solutions and adjusting the pH to 3.0 with NaOH.

Experimental

D-Penicillamine hydrochloride (Fluka) and all other chemicals (AnalaR or similar grade) were used without further purification. The stock copper(II) solution was prepared from CuSO₄·5H₂O (AnalaR). The stock solutions of HCl and NaOH (AnalaR) were prepared to adjust the pH of the solutions.

Cyclic voltammograms were recorded using a BAS CV-1B (U.S.A.) cyclic voltammetry system which also included X-Y recorder. The three-electrode cell consisted of a glassy carbon working electrode, a platinum wire auxiliary electrode and a Ag-AgCl reference electrode, to which all potentials are referred. All solutions were deoxygenated by purging extra-pure nitrogen gas before and after mixing them. The cyclic voltammograms were recorded nearly 15 min after mixing the solutions. All measurements were carried out at 30°.

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